

THE ROLE OF CULTURAL CENTERS IN THE SUBSTANTIAL ORGANIZATION OF THE POPULATION'S FREE TIME, PROBLEMS AND SHORTCOMINGS

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Annotation: Meaningful organization of cultural recreation and free time of the population, especially young people, development of folk creativity, amateur art and comprehensive support of young talents, and also Uzbek national through folk art the role of local cultural centers in preserving customs, traditions and values and passing them on to future generations.

Keywords: Leisure, cultural centers, international tourism, spirituality, enlightenment, culture, conferences, seminars, international and national exhibitions, national instruments, national handicrafts, public theater-spectacle and national games.

Introduction.

According to the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 264 dated March 30, 2019, the following are the main goals and tasks of cultural centers¹.

The main goal of the center is to further develop national culture in the Republic of Uzbekistan, to improve the quality of cultural services to the population, to satisfy their cultural needs and to ensure the meaningful passage of their free time, to promote national values, customs and traditions of creative communities. formulating exemplary programs, preserving and developing folk art and artistic amateur art, organizing various clubs, studios, courses, amateur clubs, artistic amateur teams and creating favorable conditions for their operation is shown to consist of.

To improve the quality of cultural services to the population, to satisfy their cultural needs and to ensure the meaningful passage of their free time, to form exemplary programs of creative teams that embody national values, customs and traditions; preservation and development of folk art and artistic amateur art, establishment of artistic and practical creative teams, amateur groups and creation of favorable conditions for their activity, and systematic enrichment of the creative process; attracting children to clubs, organizing courses on learning foreign languages and "speech culture", wide promotion of all genres and directions of folk art, amateur art and intangible cultural heritage and their original state conveying to the next generation and others were defined as the main tasks of cultural centers.

Today, many artists are emerging from among the participants of artistic amateur clubs and teams organized in cultural centers. Also, singing and dancing, folklore, vocal-variety, status, askiya, curiosity, trumpet-trumpet, singing, doormanship, circus, national instruments, visual and applied arts, folk theater and puppet theaters. Talents whose names are not yet known to many are identified in the competitions and festivals held in the fields, and positive work is being done to widely promote their creations.

¹ Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, No. 264 dated 30.03.2019

Competitions and shows organized on television are especially important in showing the talents of our youth. The main goal of organizing and holding exhibitions, festivals and contests that provide a wide and complete disclosure of the changes taking place in Uzbekistan, involving different layers of the population, is to attract new and talented young people. is to discover.

In the process of organizing tours, exhibitions, festivals and contests aimed at preserving and promoting the rich spiritual and cultural heritage of Uzbekistan among the population, especially among the youth, cultural centers also promote national culture in the Republic of Uzbekistan. As stated in the concept of development, we have fulfilled the task of identifying talented young people and supporting creative young people.

On December 22, 2023, an extended meeting of the Council of Spirituality and Enlightenment of the Republic was held under the leadership of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev². The effectiveness of the reforms implemented in the fields of spirituality, enlightenment, culture, art and creativity and future priority issues were discussed. Special attention was paid to cultural centers, and they emphasized that the activity of 837 existing cultural centers in our Republic is very important for improving the system of cultural recreation and meaningful spending of free time of the population.

In recent years, 43 cultural centers have been newly built in our country. 344 cultural centers have been repaired and equipped. Today, about 4,000 clubs are operating in creative centers. More than 120,000 young people are engaged in them. He said that it is commendable that about a thousand of our young people were included in 81 clubs in the cultural center of the mother city. Unfortunately, the activities of cultural centers are not effective everywhere, 167 cultural centers do not have their own buildings, 283 buildings are in a state of emergency, and there is a need for a total of eight thousand musical instruments. they waited for the governors to answer.

He said that from 2024, cultural centers with one stage, hall, library, cinema hall and club rooms will be established in each district. At the same time, the program to improve the material and technical base of more than 600 artistic amateur teams will be adopted and 100 billion soums will be allocated for it, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev said.

So, it can be seen that the attention to cultural centers will increase from now on. On the basis of the state program for the organization and support of the activities of the clubs, great opportunities are given. In turn, the prospect of organizing clubs in cultural centers is included in the programs of the Ministry of Culture, and financial financing is being carried out.

According to the decision No. 178 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 25, 2013 "On measures for the establishment of modern culture and population recreation centers in 2013-2018" No. in accordance with the decision, a total of 66 cultural centers were registered and approved in the region.

Buildings of 26 cultural centers in the cities and districts of the Khorezm region. Decision No. 178 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 25, 2013 "On measures for the establishment of modern culture and population recreation centers in 2013-2018", O Pursuant to the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4038 dated November 28, 2018 and within the framework of the "Obad Kyzhol" and "Obad

² <https://gov.uz/oz/news/view/4402/>

Mahalla" programs, 16 cultural centers are in need of repair and 22 cultural centers do not have their own buildings. .

281 clubs of more than 20 types have been organized in existing cultural centers, and the number of participants in them is 5058.

According to the use of the circles operating in the cultural centers belonging to the cultural departments of the districts and cities, 1 circle has an average of 18 participants. The participants of each of the organized clubs participate in training on the days and at the specified time based on the approved schedule.

Recreational cultural concert programs are performed by regional concert organizations and participants of famous artists and amateur folk ensembles based on the established plan in the cultural centers of the cities and districts of the region. Also, clubs for artistic amateurs, sports, and libraries and computer learning clubs were organized in cultural centers.

Address List of the Ministry of Economy of the Republic for construction, reconstruction, perfect repair and equipment works of cultural objects in Khorazy region in 2022-2026:

- in 2023, the building of the Pitnak city cultural center of Tuproqkala district, the building of the Ovshar cultural center of Khazorasp district will be rebuilt;

- In 2024, the building of the cultural center of the Urganch district will be rebuilt, the cultural center of the Shavat district will be rebuilt, the cultural center of the Gurlan district will be rebuilt;

- in 2025, the construction of the Khiva city cultural center building, the construction of the Gurlan district cultural center building, the construction of the Urganch district Goybu cultural center building;

- in 2026, the construction of the cultural center of Yangibozor district, the construction of the Ghazovot cultural center of Koshkopir district, the construction of the Katkala cultural center of Shavot district, the reconstruction of the Mirishkor cultural center of Bogot district cultural department proposals were made.

Also, 99 and 99.1 of the report of the meeting No. 17 held in extended form during the visit of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev to the Khorezm region on March 12-13, 2020 (the "control plan" for its implementation) - for the purpose of building cultural centers on the basis of public-private partnership in the centers of cities and districts in the region in order to interest young people in culture and art, and to organize their free time in a meaningful way, by the governments of cities and districts, not less than 0.5 hectares of land Decisions on allocation of plots for the Ministry of Culture were made in the prescribed manner.

References:

- 1 Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, No. 264 dated 30.03.2019
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- 3.Amanbayev, B., & Qalandarov, U. E. (2022). Yoshlar tarbiyasida teatr san'atining o'rni va ahamiyati. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 2(2), 82-87.
- 4.<https://gov.uz/oz/news/view/4402/>

